

Employment Opportunities, Aspirations and Challenges among Dalit Youth: A Sociological Analysis

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Abstract

Youth are the best human resource who can bring rapid development to the society. In different areas, youth are usually facing different kinds of problems like conditions of poverty, backwardness and unemployment is widespread. Among them, Dalit youths are the most affected section of society. They either have low educational skills or no educational skills. Due to these factors, Dalit youths are mostly engaged in minority jobs. Various rural employment and self-employment schemes implemented by the government during the past years to improve the status of Dalit youths such as the Integrated Rural Development Program (IRDP), Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA), Training of Rural Youth for Self-employment Employment Program (TRYSEM), etc in general and focusing Dalit youth in particular. In addition, government initiatives like Start-up India, and MUDRA, were launched to generate employment opportunities for the low-skilled workforce. The main objective of this study is to analyse the occupational aspirations among Dalit youth and to examine the status and implementation of rural employment programmes for Dalit youth. The paper is descriptive and exploratory based on primary data gathered from 100 Dalit youths of Bakshi-Ka-Talab of Lucknow District. This research helps to understand the status of Dalit youth in the light of employment, underemployment and unemployment. This research study also throws light on the implementation of rural employment programmes focusing on Dalit youths.

Keywords: Youth, Dalit, Employment, Challenges, Aspirations.

1. Introduction

Youth are the most enthusiastic, innovative, dynamic and vibrant population in any country and they show a strong passion and motivation which makes them valuable human resources to drive the economic, political and cultural development of the country. The future prosperity of any country depends on the number and productivity of the people employed. A skilled workforce is essential for the inclusive growth of a nation (Maqbool and Khan, 2019). Young people are most likely to be employed as they move through their life journey from adolescence to youth. The job market is a dynamic system with many people moving in and out of the system every day.

India as a nation is faced with the massive problem of unemployment. It is a social and global problem among youth and especially when we talk about Dalit Youth, it becomes a challenge from their education to employment opportunities. Each and every individual in a country wants to achieve good and well-paid employment opportunities so that they can appropriately sustain their living condition. The lack of employment opportunities can lead to poverty, social unrest and a lack of economic growth. If youth want to obtain decent employment, they must develop their competencies, capabilities and acquire quality education but despite fulfilling all the abilities and qualifications any times Dalit youth are discriminated against based on the caste system.

Dalit youth, carrying the legacy of generations burdened by social and economic marginalization, face unique challenges in navigating the labyrinth of employment opportunities. While aspirations soar, access to resources often impedes their path to success. In response, the Indian government has implemented several dedicated schemes, equipping Dalit youth with the financial tools to chart their own future. Addressing the challenges and

aspirations of Dalit youth regarding employment necessities understanding the relevant government programs that can empower them. While systematic inequalities pose hurdles, these initiatives aim to equip Dalit youth with skills, resources and access to opportunities, bridging the gap towards equitable employment. Here are some prominent programs:

A. National Scheduled Castes Finance and Development Corporation (NSFDC)

Established in 1989, NSFDC stands as a pillar of support for SC entrepreneurs, offering loans and subsidies for income-generating activities in both rural and urban areas. With an annual family income limit of Rs. 3.00 lakh for beneficiaries, the corporation caters to a diverse range of aspirations, from setting up small businesses to purchasing agricultural equipment.

B. National SafaiKaramcharis Finance and Development Corporation (NSKFDC)

Focused specifically on SafaiKaramcharis and their dependents, NSKFDC champions their socio-economic upliftment through credit support. Loans are readily available for income-generating activities such as small businesses, animal husbandry, and agriculture, empowering this often-marginalized community to break free from traditional occupations.

C. Scheme of Assistance to Scheduled Castes Development Corporations (SCDCs)

This centrally sponsored scheme acts as a catalyst for state-level SCDCs, providing them with essential share capital from both the Center and state governments. Empowered with these resources, SCDCs extend loans and subsidies to SC entrepreneurs, fostering a vibrant ecosystem of self-reliance and economic prosperity within the community.

D.Credit Enhancement Guarantee Scheme for Scheduled Castes:

Launched in 2014, this innovative scheme acts as a bridge between Dalit entrepreneurs and financial institutions. By providing credit guarantee coverage of up to 80% on loans, it mitigates the risk for banks and boosts young SC entrepreneurs' access to funds for both startups and established businesses.

E. Special Central Assistance to Scheduled Castes Sub Plan (SCA to SCSP):

Aligning with the broader goal of SC development, SCA to SCSP allocates central funds specifically for initiatives like skill development and enterprise development. While not directly offering credit facilities, these programs indirectly contribute to employment generation by equipping Dalit youth with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in the modern economy.

1.1. Dalit in India

Dalits are a group of people who have historically been marginalized and discriminated against in Indian society. The term "Dalit" comes from the Sanskrit word "dal," which means "broken" or "oppressed." Despite this Dalit youths are young people who belong to the Dalit community in India. Like other young people, they are in the process of transitioning from adolescence to adulthood and are often faced with a range of opportunities and challenges as they navigate this process.

However, Dalit youth in India face significant social and economic challenges as a result of their caste identity. One of the most pressing issues facing the youth today is unemployment, particularly among Dalit Youth. Many Dalits are excluded from the formal education system,

which limits their access to skilled jobs. Even when they do have the necessary qualifications, they also face discrimination and bias in the job market, which makes it difficult for them to secure employment. Additionally, many Dalit youth come from low-income families and lack the resources to pursue higher education or training programs. Despite these challenges, there are initiatives and schemes in place to support Dalit youth employment, such as the National Scheduled Castes Finance and Development Corporation, the National SafaiKaramcharis Finance and Development Corporation etc.

Table.1. Scheduled Castes in India

Population	201,378,372
Male	103,535,314
Female	97,843,058
Children (0-6)	14.50%
Literacy Rate	66.07%
Sex Ratio	945

Source: Census of India, 2011

Table.2. Scheduled Caste Population in Uttar Pradesh State and Lucknow District

State (UttarPradesh)		District (Lucknow)	
Male	Female	Male	Female
21,676,975	19,680,633	4,98,799	4,49,495
Total- 41,357,608		Total- 9,48,294	

Source: Census of India, 2011

1.2. Youth in India

According to the Oxford Dictionary of Sociology, Youth is typically regarded in sociology as an ascribed status, or socially constructed label, rather than simply the biological condition of being young. Youth is the stage of life between childhood and adulthood. Youth is a more fluid category than a fixed age group. The National Youth Policy 2003 defined youth, as those who belong to the age group of 13-35. Further, the National Youth Policy of 2014 defined the

youth age group as 15-29 years intending to have a more focused approach, as far as various policy interventions are concerned.

Oommen(1990) points out the various characteristics of Indian youth:

- It is an age group between 15-30 years, youth is full of psychic energy,
- They are neither conservative nor progressive in nature.
- They are ‘unattached to’ and ‘unsettled’ in society; they have not yet developed a vested interest in maintenance of the status quo.

Table.3. Dalit Youth in India

(in million)

Adolescent (10-19 years)		Youth (15-24)	
SC	% to Total Adolescent	SC	% to Total Youth
44	17.5	40	17.1

Source: Census of India, 2011

- The adolescent Population between 10 – 19 Years is 253 million in which 72% of the total adolescents in India reside in rural areas (181 million).
- The Youth Population between 15 – 24 Years is 232 million of which 68% live in rural areas.

2. Objectives of the study

The following objectives were framed for the present study:

1. To study the socio-economic status of Dalit youth.
2. To analyze the occupational aspirations among Dalit youth.
3. To examine the implementation of rural employment programmes for Dalit youth.

3. Theoretical Perspective

This research paper employs a subaltern approach to dissect the complex interplay between employment opportunities, aspirations, and challenges faced by Dalit youth in India. Subaltern studies, as championed by scholars like Ranajit Guha and Gayatri Spivak, foreground the experiences and perspectives of marginalized groups often rendered voiceless by dominant social structures. This lens resonates deeply with the present study, as it seeks to amplify the narratives of Dalit youth, a traditionally silenced community grappling with historical inequalities and contemporary limitations.

To illuminate the lived realities of Dalit youth in search of employment and fulfillment, the study draws upon the foundational work of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, the iconic Dalit leader and architect of India's Constitution. Ambedkar's writings on caste annihilation and systemic discrimination provide a historical and ideological framework for understanding the persistent challenges faced by Dalit youth in accessing decent employment opportunities. His emphasis on the need for affirmative action and social reform remains essential in the ongoing struggle for Dalit empowerment.

Furthering this subaltern critique, Spivak's concept of the "subaltern as a speaking subject" underscores the importance of listening to and validating the experiences of Dalit youth directly. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions, integral to this research, become tools for privileging Dalit voices and deconstructing the dominant narratives that often obscure their aspirations and struggles.

By weaving together the insights of Ambedkar, Spivak, and other subaltern theorists, this research seeks to move beyond mere description and towards a nuanced understanding of the

structural forces shaping the employment options, aspirations, and challenges faced by Dalit youth. This subaltern perspective not only gives voice to their experiences but also offers a critical lens for challenging hegemonic structures and working towards a more equitable society where Dalit youth can pursue their aspirations and realize their full potential.

4. Literature Review

Kumar (2022) in his research study tries to understand the potential of employment creation through the government run PMKVY scheme and to analyse the success of the skill development program among people from lower income groups with special reference to the skilling centre in Allahabad district of Uttar Pradesh. The study has concluded that the scheme has become popular and is likely to be shared among aspirants. The study has also concluded that an equal number of students from both genders enroll on the skilling program.

Sonkar (2021) conducted a study on "Evaluation of Government Policies and Programmes for the Welfare of Dalits: A Review". The objectives of the study were to critically evaluate the policies and programs and find out behind reason for the failure of these policies and programmes. The study has concluded that the government schemes meant for the SC community are not being implemented properly due to a lack of awareness and education, and deficiencies in policy making. This is leading to economic inequality among Dalits, inequality at the level of education and culture, and inequality based on region, which is a question mark on the policymaking of the schemes.

Kumar (2021) in his research paper "Youth, Higher Education, and Employment: A Case Study of Jharkhand State" aims to analyze the condition of higher education in Jharkhand and its impact on youth and employment. This study is a case study of Nilamber Pitamber

University of Jharkhand. The study has concluded that students of the university are not satisfied with the education system and 89% of them want to migrate to other cities for better education and preparation for competitive exams. The study has also concluded that most students believe that government jobs are better than private jobs as government jobs provide job security and fixed salaries.

Satish (2021) studied the educational and occupational variation among the past and present generations. The data were collected from 102 Dalit youth respondents via interview method. The researcher found that the majority of the parents of the respondents are illiterates and some completed the primary to secondary level of education and over half of the Dalit youth respondents are graduates. The present study concluded that education has a significant role in changing the status of individuals.

Chandrashekhar and Shivanna (2020) in their paper "A Sociological Study of Rural Youth in Karnataka" focused on rural Dalit youth and their socio-economic, political, educational and occupational conditions. This study is a pilot survey conducted in Chitradurga district of Karnataka. The study concluded that youths are influenced by media and new technology and there is a cultural change along with drastic change in fashion style, behavior and so on. The study also analyzed that the rural youth of Karnataka can recognize the problem and solve that problem.

Kedar (2020) in his paper entitled "Youth in India: Education and Employment" focused on the status of the Indian Youth in their education and employment. This study is based on secondary source data. The present study analyzed that in 2014 73.3 million youth were unemployed which accounted for 37.7 percent of the global unemployed.

Biswakarma and Mangrati (2017) in their study intended to identify the current employment status of educated Dalit youth and the employment perception of employed Dalit youth in Nepal. The study revealed that most of the Dalit youth were found to be satisfied with their current jobs and those who were dissatisfied with their jobs were mostly due to mismatch in their salary, job security, lack of opportunity for career progression, work area and field of study. It has also been concluded that a large number of Dalit youth perceived themselves as underemployed due to a lack of their competencies and skills, mismatch in the field of work and field of study, lack of experience in the respective field, lack of self-exploration and career counselling as well as caste discrimination.

Kumar (2016) in his article focuses on educated unemployed youth from different socio-economic backgrounds, struggle for employment and engagement with politics and religion in the era of neo-liberalism. The present study is a multi-site ethnographic fieldwork conducted between June 2013 and August 2016 in Allahabad and Meerut. The study revealed that the spectre of unemployment has increased the sense of insecurity among the youth and deepened their identity crisis. The study also revealed that youth in UP were not only engaged in social services, but also challenged existing inequalities by fighting against everyday caste discrimination in the university and outside the university.

Kabir (2016) in his study covering the Salai village of Ghaziabad in UP focuses on the meaning of education and job opportunities for Muslim youths about their educational qualifications and social position in the hierarchy of the Muslim class and Caste groups, with special reference to the community of Uttar Pradesh. It was concluded from this study that Muslim youth used to do agricultural or non-agricultural work along with studies. e.g. selling buffalo milk in nearby villages. This leads to muslims underrepresentation in regular white-

collar and governmental jobs.

Saini (2015), conducted a study titled "Skill Development in India: Need, Challenges and Way Forward". The main objective of the study was to study the current skill potential of India, study the challenges faced by the skill development system in India and suggest possible solutions or ways forward. The study concluded that "India's transition to one of the largest and fastest growing global economies has been a remarkable event during the last decade. To maintain its growth trajectory, an efficient and continuous system of skill development for its workforce is essential for India. To take advantage of the demographic dividend, India will need to empower its workforce with the right kind of skills. There is a need to increase the capacity and capability of skill development programmes.

Acharya et al. (2010) conducted a study on "Level and Trend of Youth Unemployment and Population Change in India and Selected States". The study focused on the level and trends of unemployment among youth in India and selected states. The study revealed that youth unemployment has increased over time and educated youth living in urban centers are more prone to the problem of unemployment. The study also revealed that infrastructure and urbanization have greater potential to reduce the unemployment crisis among the youth.

Vicziany (2005) conducted a study entitled "Dalit Responses to Unemployment in Contemporary India". The present paper is an in-depth study of some urban Dalits. The paper focused on the aspirations of college-educated Dalits about the rising unemployment and the consequences of extreme socio-economic pressure. The study has concluded that higher education has become an integral aspiration amongst Dalit students regardless of the inability of employment to match economic growth and a great increase in graduate unemployment.

This shows a positive as well as negative development of Dalits in India.

5. Methods and Technique

This research, adopting a descriptive and exploratory approach, delves into the employment opportunities, challenges, and aspirations of Dalit youth in villages situated within the Bakshika-talab block of Lucknow District, Uttar Pradesh. To capture the lived experiences and diverse perspectives of this population, primary data was collected through interviews conducted with a purposive sample of 100 respondents and secondary data had been used to comprehensively understand the population demographics and readily available employment programs specifically targeting Dalit communities.

The purposive sampling strategy focused on Dalit youth aged 18-35 both male and female, encompassing a crucial period of life where choices regarding education, employment, and life goals are often made. The interview schedule covered pertinent themes like socio-economic status, educational attainment, occupational aspirations, employment experiences, and awareness of rural employment programs.

6. Results and Findings

Table.4. Distribution of the respondents by Gender and Subcaste

Gender	Frequency N=100	Sub-caste			
		Chamar	Pasi	Dhanuk	Raidas
Male	45 (45%)	27 (45.8%)	10 (50%)	3 (43%)	5 (35.7%)
Female	55 (55%)	32 (54.2%)	10 (50%)	4 (57%)	9 (64.3%)
Total	100 (100%)	59 (59%)	20 (20%)	7 (7%)	14 (14%)

*Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

Table 4 reveals a near-equal distribution of respondents by gender, with 45 males and 55 females participating. Among males, Chamar respondents are the most numerous (27), followed by Pasi (10), Dhanuk (3), and Raidas (5). A similar pattern emerges for females, with Chamar again forming the largest group (32), followed by Pasi (10), Dhanuk (4), and Raidas (9). These findings suggest that caste distribution is relatively balanced across genders within the sampled population.

Table.5. Distribution of the respondents by Age & Educational Status

Age	Frequency N=100	Educational Status					
		Below Matriculate	Matriculate	First Year	Intermediate	Graduation	Illiterate
18-20	21 (21%)	2 (8.7%)	3 (13%)	2 (100%)	11 (39%)	2 (10%)	1 (20%)
21-23	19 (19%)	5 (21.7%)	4 (19%)	0 (0)	4 (14.3%)	5 (25%)	1 (20%)
24-26	20 (20%)	5 (21.7%)	2 (9%)	0 (0)	4 (14.3%)	7 (35%)	2 (40%)
27-29	16 (16%)	3 (13%)	4 (19%)	0 (0)	6 (21.4%)	3 (15%)	0 (0)
30 & above	24 (24%)	8 (34.9%)	9 (40%)	0 (0)	3 (11%)	3 (15%)	1 (20%)
Total	100 (100%)	23 (23%)	22 (22%)	2 (2%)	28 (28%)	20 (20%)	5 (5%)

*Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

Table 5 reveals a clear inverse relationship between age and educational attainment. As age groups climb, we witness a consistent decline in higher educational completion. While the youngest group (18-20) boasts 11 intermediate completions and 2 graduations, older groups demonstrate progressively fewer graduates: 5 in the 21-23 group, 7 in the 24-26 group, 3 in the 27-29 group, and just 3 in the 30 & above group. This trend is further underscored by the increasing prevalence of lower educational levels in older age groups. For instance, while only 2 respondents aged 18-20 lack basic literacy or hold qualifications below matriculation, this number shoots up to 8 in the 30 & above group.

Table.6. Distribution of Respondents by Age, Gender and Marital Status

Age	Frequency N=100	Gender					
		Male			Female		
		Married	Unmarried	Widowed	Married	Unmarried	Widowed
18-20	20 (20%)	0 (0)	10 (43%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	10 (35%)	0 (0)
21-23	19 (19%)	0 (0)	8 (35%)	0 (0)	2 (8%)	8 (27%)	0 (0)
24-26	20 (20%)	6 (28.6%)	5 (22%)	0 (0)	3 (12%)	6 (21%)	0 (0)
27-29	16 (16%)	5 (24%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (20%)	5 (17%)	1 (50%)
30 & above	24 (24%)	10 (48%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	15 (60%)	0 (0)	1 (50%)
Total	100 (100%)	21 (29%)	23 (23%)	0 (0)	25 (25%)	29 (29%)	2 (2%)

*Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

Table 6 shows that among the 55 female respondents, unmarried respondents dominate with 29 falling within this category. The age group for unmarried female skews younger, with 10 between 18 and 20, 6 between 24 and 26, and 8 between 21 and 23. Only 5 fall within the 27-29 age bracket. Married women, on the other hand, are mostly found in the older age group, with 15 out of 25 falling at 30 years and above. Only 2 female are married within the 21-23 age range and 3 between 24-29. Notably, no married female are found in the youngest age group of 18-20. 2 respondent widows are present, one in each of the 27-29 and 30 years age groups. For the 45 male respondents, a similar pattern emerges with unmarried individuals constituting the majority, with 23 falling within this category. The age distribution mirrors that of females, with 10 within the 18-20 age group, 8 between 21-23, and 5 between 24-26. Married male are again concentrated in the older age group, with 10 out of 21 falling at 30

years and above. Notably, no married male are found in the youngest age group of 18-20. Six married male are found within the 24-26 age range and 5 between 27-29.

Table.7. Distribution of Respondents by Educational and Occupational Status

Educational Status	Frequency N=100	Occupational Status						
		Agricultural Sector	Unemployed	Labour	Private Sector	Engaged in Home Duties	Looking for employment	Studying
Below Matriculate	22 (23%)	10 (40%)	2 (12.5%)	6 (28.6%)	0 (0)	4 (28.5%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Matriculate	22 (22%)	6 (24%)	3 (18.75%)	7 (33.3%)	0 (0)	6 (42.8%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
First Year	2 (2%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (8.3%)
Intermediate	28 (28%)	6 (24%)	6 (37.5%)	7 (33.3%)	1 (33.3)	3 (21.4%)	2 (22.3%)	3 (25%)
Graduation	21 (20%)	0 (0)	4 (25%)	0 (0)	2 (66.7)	0 (0)	7 (77.3%)	8 (66.7%)
Illiterate	5 (5%)	3 (12%)	1 (6.25)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (7.1%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	100 (100%)	25 (25%)	16 (16%)	21 (21%)	3 (3%)	14 (14%)	9 (9%)	12 (12%)

*Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

*Source: Primary Data

Figure.1. Educational Attainments

Educational attainment plays a crucial role in shaping occupational opportunities and outcomes. Higher levels of education equip individuals with specialized skills and knowledge, making them more competitive in the job market and eligible for higher-paying positions. This relationship between education and occupation is clearly reflected in the data from **Table 7**. The analysis reveals that the majority of respondents i.e., 25 respondents are engaged in the agricultural sector, with lower educational levels dominating this group. 10 respondents with agricultural occupations have not completed middle school (Below Matriculate), 6 respondents hold a high school diploma (Matriculate), and 6 respondents have completed intermediate college (Intermediate). Notably, there are no respondents with a graduate degree working in agriculture, highlighting the limited opportunities for upward mobility within this sector for higher-educated individuals. Interestingly, unemployment is also prevalent among respondents with intermediate education, with six out of 16 falling in this category. This suggests that simply attaining a certain level of education may not guarantee employment,

further emphasizing the need for relevant skills and job opportunities aligned with educational qualification. Moving toward other occupations, we see a shift in educational profiles. For instance, all 3 respondents in private jobs hold at least an intermediate degree, while 7 out of eight graduates are currently studying or looking for employment. This pattern confirms the positive correlation between higher education and access to professional occupations or continued education. The data also shows that with 14 respondents categorized as "home duties" holding either a below-matriculate or matriculate level education. In conclusion, the distribution of respondents across occupations and educational levels paints a multifaceted picture. While agriculture remains a common occupation for those with lower education, opportunities in other sectors appear to favor higher educational attainment. The presence of unemployed individuals with intermediate education also raises questions about skill mismatch and job market dynamics. Overall, the data highlights the complex interplay between education and occupation, emphasizing the need for further investigation into factors influencing career pathways and socioeconomic mobility.

Table.8. Distribution of Respondents' Occupational Aspirations by Gender

Aspirations	Frequency N=100	Gender	
		Male	Female
Agricultural Sector	13 (13%)	7 (15.5%)	6 (11%)
Labour or Manual Job	16 (16%)	9 (20%)	7 (13%)
Government Job	9 (9%)	4 (9%)	5 (9%)
Private Job	5 (5%)	1 (2.2%)	4 (8%)
Any Job	36 (36%)	19 (42.2%)	17 (30%)
Professional	4 (4%)	2 (4.4%)	2 (4%)
No Aspiration	17 (17%)	3 (6.7%)	14 (25%)
Total	100 (100%)	45 (45%)	55 (55%)

*Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

*Source: Primary Data

Figure.2. Occupational Aspirations by Gender

Occupational aspirations are important because they influence an individual’s educational and career choices, which in turn impact their future income, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. Understanding respondents’ occupational aspirations can help policymakers, educators, and career counselors develop programs and interventions to support individuals in achieving their career goals. It is clear from the **Table 8** that out of 100 respondents, 13 aspire for a career in the agriculture sector, with a gender breakdown of 7 males and 6 females. The majority of respondents i.e., 36 respondents desire any kind of job, indicating a focus on earning income, with 19 males and 17 females. 17 respondents have no specific occupational aspirations. 16 respondents seek labour or manual jobs. The remaining 9 respondents have government job as a aspirations. This data suggests that respondents prioritize job security and income earning potential in their occupational aspirations. While some aspire for specific sectors like agriculture or manual labour, a significant portion remains undecided or open to any job opportunities. This highlights the need for career guidance and support to help individuals explore their options and make informed decisions about their future careers.

Table.9. Reason for no occupational aspirations among Respondents

Reasons	Frequency N=17	Gender	
		Male	Female
Due to Lack of Education	13 (76.5%)	4 (23.5%)	9 (53%)
Due to Poverty	8 (47%)	5 (29.4%)	3 (17.6%)
Due to Lack of Awareness	7 (41.2%)	1 (6%)	6 (35.2%)
Engaged in Home Duties	11 (64.7%)	1 (6%)	10 (59%)

* Source: Primary Data

**Parentheses indicates percentage

*** Table based on multiple responses

*Source: Primary Data

* Table based on multiple responses

Figure.3. Working Nature

Examining the reasons behind respondents' lack of occupational aspirations reveals a web of interconnected factors rather than isolated individual circumstances. While 11 respondents cite their engagement in home duties as the sole constraint, this likely intersects with other elements like limited education or societal expectations, hindering their ability to consider future career paths. Similarly, the 7 respondents who blame lack of awareness may also face poverty or educational barriers that restrict their exposure to diverse career options.

Poverty emerges as a potent force, with 8 respondents attributing their lack of aspirations directly to its grip. The financial burden likely limits their access to education, skill development, and even basic information about potential careers, trapping them in a cycle of limited opportunity. This factor resonates with the 13 respondents who view their lack of education as the primary obstacle, suggesting that poverty and educational attainment are intricately linked in impacting future aspirations.

*Source: Primary Data

Figure.4. Awareness about Rural Employment Programmes among Respondents

The data reveals a significant disparity in awareness about rural employment programmes among different age groups. While 43 respondents acknowledged awareness of these schemes, the remaining 53 respondents, were unaware with them. Within the aware group, age brackets of 18-20 and 21-23 showed the participation, each contributing 9 respondents. Age groups 24-26 and 27-29 followed with 11 and 8 respondents, respectively, while the 30 and above age group had the lowest participation with 6 respondents. Among those unaware of the schemes, the 30 and above age group again had the highest number of respondents at 19. Age groups

24-26 and 27-29 followed with 10 and 8 respondents, respectively. Interestingly, the 18-20 and 21-23 age groups, which showed strong awareness initially, had a relatively lower number of unaware respondents, at 11 and 9 each.

These findings suggest that younger generations might be more receptive to information about rural employment programmes, while older age groups might require more targeted outreach efforts. Additionally, the data hints at a potential correlation between age and knowledge level, with younger respondents generally being more informed about these schemes. Further investigation is needed to confirm this correlation and understand the underlying factors influencing awareness levels across different age groups.

* Source: Primary Data

Figure.5. Respondents Registered in Employment Exchange Office

The data paints a concerning picture of low engagement with the Employment Exchange Office. Only 4 out of 100 respondents, were registered with the service. This meagre participation is further concerning when we consider the gender breakdown: 3 females and 1

male, highlighting a potential lack of reach among men. The most alarming finding, however, is that none of the registered individuals reported receiving any assistance from the office, rendering its effectiveness questionable.

The vast majority, of 96 respondents were not registered, primarily due to a critical lack of awareness. This suggests a crucial need for increased outreach and education efforts to inform the population about the Employment Exchange Office and the services it offers. Without proper knowledge, individuals cannot leverage the potential benefits of this resource.

7. Conclusion

This study has shed light on various socio-economic aspects of a specific rural community, revealing complex interrelationships between factors like caste, gender, age, education, occupation, and aspirations. While caste distribution appears relatively balanced across genders, a clear inverse relationship emerges between age and educational attainment. The data presents a multifaceted picture of occupational distribution, with agriculture dominating for those with lower education levels, while higher education seems to favor professional occupations or continued education. However, the presence of unemployed individuals with intermediate education raises questions about skill mismatches and job market dynamics. Overall, the interplay between education and occupation emerges as intricate, requiring further investigation into factors influencing career pathways and socioeconomic mobility.

Occupational aspirations often influence an individual's life trajectory. This study reveals a prioritization of job security and income earning potential, with a majority desiring "any kind of job." While some aspire for specific sectors, a significant portion remains undecided or unaware of options, highlighting the need for career guidance and support. Reasons for

lacking aspirations are multi-faceted, with poverty, limited education, and lack of awareness about rural employment programs playing key roles. Interestingly, younger generations seem more informed about these schemes, suggesting a potential age-knowledge correlation that warrants further exploration.

A final concerning finding is the low engagement with the Employment Exchange Office. This service, potentially crucial for navigating the job market, remains largely unknown and underutilized by the community. Increased outreach and education efforts are essential to bridge this gap and ensure individuals reap the potential benefits of available resources.

In conclusion, this study provides a valuable snapshot of the socio-economic realities within a rural community, drawing attention to several crucial areas for further research and intervention. Addressing the complex interplay of factors influencing education, occupation, aspirations, and access to resources can empower individuals and ultimately pave the way for a more equitable and prosperous future.

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